

Rapid determination of hexavalent chromium in ppb level and speciation analysis of the metal with a organic reagent, bis(pyrrole-2-aldehyde)-thiocarbohydrazone (BPATCH) in presence of vanadium(V)

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Abstract : The organic compound bis(pyrrole-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone (BPATCH) produced instant green coloured complex at room temperature with chromium(VI) in acid medium and the intensity of the green colour enhanced quantitatively with the addition of vanadium(V). It is a complexation reaction and speciation of chromium(VI) and chromium(III) is possible because the reagent produced no colour reaction with chromium(III). The suitable acidity range for the green coloured chromium(VI) or blue green coloured vanadium added chromium(VI) complexes is 0.01–0.5 (N) HCl or 0.3 to 2.2 pH. Molar absorptivity of the blue green complex is $2.14 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 590 nm and Sandell sensitivity is $0.0025 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. A linear working range from the detection limit to 300 ng/ml of chromium(VI) was obtained. The lower detection limit (LOD) for the chromium-BPATCH complex and chromium-vanadium-BPATCH complex were 20 ppb and 5 ppb respectively at room temperature, when the absorbance of the colour reaction was 0.002 at 590 nm. The proposed spectrophotometric method was successfully applied to the determination of chromium(VI) in industrial effluent, USGS rock standard and speciation of chromium(VI) and chromium(III) in ground water sample.

Keywords : Hexavalent chromium, BPATCH, speciation analysis, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

The carcinogenicity^{1,2} and mutagenicity of chromium(VI) have been a matter of concern and it is well established that Cr^{VI} readily passes into cell via anion channel³ and within the cell it is eventually reduced by cellular components to Cr^V, Cr^{IV} to Cr^{III} species^{4,5}. But the system which reduce the Cr^{VI} are yet unknown as are the final product of the reaction⁶. However microsomes are capable of reducing Cr^{VI} and in this case Cr^V species of considerable stability have been observed⁷. Glutathione⁸ is an intercellular peptide, which is important in the maintenance of red-ox status and may it be an active intercellular toxin to damage cells. In course of toxicity chromium(VI) compound interferes the enzymatic sulfur uptake of the cell and affects lung, liver and kidney⁹ and insoluble chromium(VI) compounds retained in the lungs over an extended period of time cause lung cancer¹⁰. Chromium(III) species is not carcinogenic but it

may be produced as an end product of a red-ox reaction within the human cell and the intermediate species are very much harmful to any living cell^{11,12}. So to determine Cr^{VI} and speciation of the metal is nowadays work when environmental pollution and lung cancer paced rapidly to the society. We know in natural water Cr species is mainly depend upon the pH of the medium, above 7 pH Cr^{III} predominates and below 6 pH, Cr^{VI} is the major species, and in the environment air chromium particulate matter played a drastic role.

So to determine Cr^{VI} in ppb level and for speciation of the metal is an important work. And we introduce a very sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method using the organic reagent bis(pyrrole-2-aldehyde)-thiocarbohydrazone, BPATCH, which reacts in dilute HCl acid medium or in low pH and which may supersede various established methods like electro-thermal/flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry ICP-MS/ICP-AES

technique. None of them can distinguish Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} directly or these expensive methods require reagent back up to determine both species¹³⁻¹⁵. The most used spectrophotometric method is diphenyl picazide method¹⁶ but Hg, Fe and vanadium interferences are there. The method which followed pre-concentration of coloured complex on citin¹⁷ or the determination of hexavalent chromium by ultra sonication and strong anion exchange solid phase extraction method¹⁸ or speciation of chromium with cryptand ether² are good and sensitive but all those are complicated process.

On the other hand the reagent BPATCH, instantly produces a deep green colour with Cr^{VI} in dilute HCl medium and the intensity of colour enhances much more with the addition of V^{V} . Here a simple red-ox colour reaction through complexation may takes place. This intense colour reaction and complexation helps to determine the Cr^{VI} in nanogram level. The reagent is specific for speciation of Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} in solution and the method is more simple than other reported methods^{19,20}. With this method we successfully determine total chromium in the form of chromium(VI) in USGS rock standards and industrial effluent from the treatment plant of Hindustan Motor Ltd., West Bengal, India.

Experimental

Reagents :

All reagents were of analytical reagent grade. De-ionised waters were used through out.

Stock standard solutions of Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} (1 g/L) were prepared by dissolving potassium dichromate and chromium sulphate in de-ionised water and standardised by flame atomic absorption method following proper dilution.

Vanadium(V) solution (1 g/L) was prepared from NaVO_3 (J. Mathey) by dissolving it in concentrated H_2SO_4 and proper dilution with de-ionised water. The vanadium content was standardised by AAS method. Diverse metal ion solutions and non metal solutions were made with de-ionised water from respective salts.

Bis(pyrrole-2-aldehyde)thiocarbohydrazone, BPATCH, the organic compound was synthesized following standard procedure²¹ i.e. by condensation of pyrrole-2-aldehyde (2 mole) of Alpha-Aesar and thiocarbohydrazide²²

(1 mole) and recrystallised from ethanol and used as a chelating agent. Melting point of the grey coloured shining crystal was 200 °C which melts with decomposition and soluble in ethanol. A solution of 5×10^{-3} M of BPATCH in spec pure ethanol was prepared for the experiment.

Dilute hydrochloric acid was used for acidity adjustment.

Apparatus :

A Hitachi 3210 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell was used for absorbance measurement. Perkin-Elmer Analyst 100 AAS was used for standardisation and comparison of chromium content. Antonn Paar multiwave 3000 was used for rock sample digestion.

Procedure :

To an aliquot of solution containing 2–10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Cr^{VI} , 5 fold molar excess of BPATCH in ethanol was added and acidity was adjusted between 0.01–0.5 N with dilute HCl. The solution was taken in a 50 ml graduated corning glass tube. Instant green coloured chromium complex was produced, to this complex solution 5–10 fold molar excess of vanadium(V) solution was added. The green colour was changed to intense blue green colour. Intensity of colour improved largely. The volume of the mixture was made up to 20 ml with de-ionized water and it was allowed to stand for 5 min to attain the maximum complexation and then Cr^{VI} content was measured using an appropriate reagent blank at 590 nm.

Preparation of rock solution : The United States Geological Survey (USGS) rock standards (PCC-1, MAG-1) as the rock samples were digested on Antonn Parr Multi wave 3000 digestion system by recommended procedure²³. The air dried rock powders (0.5 g) were taken in the digestion vessels and required amount of $\text{HF} : \text{HNO}_3 : \text{HBO}_3$ mixture was added to it and the digestion mechanism was followed.

After digestion, the solutions were transferred in 50 ml plastic volumetric flask and the volume was made up with de-ionized water.

Preparation of industrial effluent as a test solution : 50 ml of industrial effluent from Hindustan Motor Ltd., West Bengal, India was taken on a beaker and digested on a hot plate for 10 min with addition of 1 ml con-

centrated HNO₃ and filtered through Whatman 40 and volume was made up to 50 ml for testing.

All the solutions were tested on spectrophotometer at 590 nm against a reagent blank following the above mentioned procedure.

Results and discussion

Optimization of complex formation : The optimum time required for the green coloured complex formation of Cr-BPATCH was investigated for a different time period and shown in Fig. 1. It was observed that 5 min was sufficient for the complete complex formation. The ab-

sorbance remain unchanged for 2 h and there after changed slowly owing to the decomposition of the complex. Maximum absorption of the blue green coloured Cr-V-BPATCH complex was observed on 566–570 nm, Fig. 2. All absorbance data were measured at 590 nm because excess vanadium (if added) produced a faint pink colour in the reagent blank.

Optimum acidity for complex formation was measured and it was 0.01–0.5 N HCl or in 0.3 to 2.2 pH range which produced maximum absorbance and stable complex.

Composition of the complex : The composition of green

Fig. 1. Effect of vanadium concentration with time in the Cr-V-BPATCH complexation.

Fig. 2. Abs-wavelength curve of Cr^{VI}-BPATCH complex (II) and Cr^{VI}-V-BPATCH complex (I), Cr concentration 1.25 ppm.

coloured Cr : BPATCH complex was 1 : 2 metal : ligand and the blue green vanadium added complex also showed the Cr : BPATCH ratio as 1 : 2. It was determined by mole ratio²⁴ method and verified by slope ratio method as shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. The maximum colour formation was attained when chromium to reagent ratio exceeded 1 : 2 or more and the excess reagent had no adverse effect in the absorbance value.

Cr-BPATCH and Cr-V-BPATCH complex may be cationic on nature. Passing through Amberlite 120 column in 0.5 N HCl medium, both the complexes were absorbed totally in the column bed. Washed of water was

measured in FAAS and no chromium was found.

Extractibility : None of the green Cr^{VI}-BPATCH complex or vanadium added Cr^{VI} complex was extractable in any organic solvent. Only they were partly soluble in acetonitrile and completely soluble in hot DMF.

Calibration graph, detection limit, precision : The calibration graph is linear up to 300 ng/mL. The Sandell sensitivity²⁵ was 0.0025 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ for Cr-V-BPATCH complex. Molar absorptivity of this complex was $2.1 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 590 nm. The detection limit for the Cr-BPATCH complex was 20 ppb and for the Cr-V-BPATCH complex it was 5 ppb where the absorbances of

Fig. 3. Mole ratio curve of Cr-V-BPATCH complex.

Fig. 4. Composition study by slope ratio method.

the colour reactions are 0.002.

The standard deviation of five parallel determinations of 2 µg/ml of Cr^{VI} was 0.18.

Effect of foreign ions : To evaluate the selectivity of the method chromium(VI) was estimated with the said reagent in presence of commonly associated base metals or other anions. As the alkali metals had no interference so they were not incorporated. The tolerance limit was set as the conc. of the foreign ions that produced a variation in the apparent recovery of 2 µg/ml of Cr^{VI} less than 5 times the RSD (i.e. variation ≤ ±5).

Experiment showed that the metals such as Ti⁴⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Al³⁺, Co³⁺ are tolerated at 500 fold molar excess and Mn²⁺, Sb³⁺, Cd²⁺, Pb²⁺ has no interferences upto 100 fold molar excesses. V⁵⁺, Cr³⁺, Hg²⁺, can be tolerated upto 10 fold molar excess without adding any extractant or masking agent.

Common anions such as Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, CH₃COO⁻ had been tolerated upto 1000 time molar excess. KI can be tolerated up to 5 fold molar excess. Interference from strong reducing agents, S₂O₃²⁻, or heavy metals with variable valencies could be minimized by warming the

test solution with dilute KMNO₄ or HNO₃ prior to estimate.

Determination of chromium in real sample and speciation analysis of the metal :

The proposed method was tested by applying it to the determination of Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} in drinking water sample (ground water and tap water). The water samples were collected from deep tube well water and tap water of Presidency University and spiked with 10, 20, 40 µg/L of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} respectively and estimated by proposed method and recovered successfully with the method. Cr^{VI} was estimated at first and other part of the sample was boiled with marginal amount of dilute KMnO₄ and tested further for Cr^{VI} and the difference was reported for Cr^{III} contribution and shown in Table 1. As can be seen in the table that neither of the sample were contaminated for Cr^{III} or Cr^{VI}. The recovery ranged between 95 to 105% showing good precision.

Cr^{VI} in USGS rock solution as well as industrial effluent were estimated by the method successfully and the results were given in the Table 2 were in good agreement with certified and standardized value.

Table 1. Recovery studies of Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} added to drinking water sample

Drinking water sample	Chromium species	Conc. in water (µg ml ⁻¹)	Conc. added (µg ml ⁻¹)	Found (µg ml ⁻¹)	Recovery (%)
(A) Tap water, College St., Kolkata	Cr ^{VI}	Not detectable	10 .0	9.5 ± 0.5	95.0
			20.0	19.6 ± 0.25	98.0
			40.0	40.2 ± 0.2	100.5
(B) Deep tube well water, College St., Kolkata	Cr ^{VI}	Not detectable	10 .0	9.6 ± 0.6	96.0
			20.0	19.9 ± 0.3	99.5
			40.0	40.4 ± 0.25	101.0
(A) Tap water, College St., Kolkata	Cr ^{III}	Not detectable	10.0	9.8 ± 0.4	98.0
			20.0	19.7 ± 0.35	98.5
			40.0	39.8 ± 0.2	99.5
(B) Deep tube well water, College St., Kolkata	Cr ^{III}	Not detectable	10.0	10.5 ± 0.6	105.0
			20.0	20.2 ± 0.3	101.0
			40.0	39.6 ± 0.25	99.0

R.S.D > ±5 for 5 sets of experiments.

Table 2. Determination of chromium content in USGS rock standards and industrial effluent

Sample	Total chromium (ppm)	Certified/estimated* value (ppm)	% Recovery
Rock PCC-1	2350 ± 4.0	2370	99.15
Rock Mag-1	110 ± 2.2	104	105.7
Industrial effluent	16.58 ± 0.2	17.0*	97.5

*Estimated by AAS method

R.S.D > ±5
from 5 sets of experiments

Conclusion

An easy, sensitive and accurate method was developed with BPATCH for the determination and speciation of chromium. No serious interferences from any commonly associated metals and non-metals. Strong reducing agents and heavy metals with variable oxidation states have some interference but these can be eliminated by dilute nitric acid digestion or with simple extraction prior to Cr^{VI} determination. The main advantages of this procedure are the following : (i) no need of ultra-pure water or chemicals, (ii) no need of solvent extraction except to minimize heavy metal interference, (iii) instant coloration takes place, therefore through put time is short, (iv) precise analysis and speciation is possible, (v) handling of multiple sample in short time is possible like any other direct instrumental method (AAS) but cost of analysis is low.

This approach helps to avoid sophisticated instrumentation and tedious extraction procedure but affords rapidity and reproducibility.

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